

Chemical Constituents of the Essential Oil of *Inula royleana*

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Manuscript received 21 November 1977, revised 15 March 1978, accepted 3 April 1978

The roots of *Inula royleana* contains 1% essential oil which on analysis by tlc and glc was found to contain eudesmol, elemol, farnesol, nerolidol, geraniol, borneol, α -terpineol, anisic alcohol, cineol, methyl heptenone, citronellal, cinnamaldehyde, β -caryophyllene, β -elemene, γ -elemene, limonene, geranyl acetate, caryophyllene oxide, β -selinene, α -selinene, δ -cadinene and unidentified compound with m.p. 145-47°.

THE roots of *Inula royleana* (compositae) are known to exhibit hypotensive activity and stimulate the peristaltic movements of intestines¹. Earlier investigations on the roots of this species revealed the presence of alkaloids^{2,4} and diterpenoids³, presence of essential oil or its chemical constituents has not been reported so far from this species¹. In this communication we wish to report the chemical constituents of the essential oil of this species.

Roots of *Inula royleana* (1 kg) were exhaustively extracted with light pet. ether (60-80°). The extract on concentration yielded 30 gms. of brownish viscous mass which when subjected to steam distillation gave 10gms. of the oil. The oil was found to have following physicochemical constants :

d_{20}^{20} 1.0202, n_D^{20} 1.6462, acid value 44.91 ; ester value 26.38 ester value after acetylation 128.34 and carbonyl value 22.06. The oil was then studied with the help of tlc over silica gel G using different solvent systems. Tlc revealed this oil to be of very complex nature but some of its constituents were identified by running authentic samples for comparison and using vanillin sulphuric acid and 2 : 4 dinitrophenylhydrazine as spray reagents. The following components were identified by tlc :

Eudesmol, elemol, farnesol, nerolidol, α -terpeniol, cineol, geraniol, methyl heptenone, geranyl acetate, borneol, anisic alcohol and caryophyllene oxide. The oil was then exhaustively studied by glc.

Gas liquid chromatography of the oil :

Glc of the oil was done on PE 881 having stainless steel column 6 ft. long containing SE-30 and FID. The operation was done at a programmed rate of 90-200° with 6°/min. using nitrogen as the carrier gas. The compounds in the gas chromatogram were identified by comparison of their retention times with those of the reference samples.

The identified compounds along with their percentage are—

Limonene (0.76), Cineol (0.33), Methyl heptenone (0.63), Citronellal (0.16), Borneol (0.28), α -Terpeniol (0.14), Geraniol (0.79), Geranyl acetate (0.06), Caryophyllene oxide (1.37), β -Selinene (12.54), α -Selinene (4.28), β -Caryophyllene (3.70), β -Elemene (8.00), γ -Elemene (12.44), Nerolidol (6.81), Elemol (3.37), Cinnamaldehyde (1.73), Anisic alcohol (4.12), Eudesmol (1.25), Farnesol (4.43), Anisaldehyde (2.55), Alantolactone (6.34) and Isoalantolactone (4.95).

The oil was chromatographed over a silica gel column. Fractions 37-42 and 45-50 eluted with benzene yielded white solid which on crystallisation from methanol gave white crystalline compounds with m.p. 145-48° (7 mg) and 60-62°. The first compound could not be identified due to its low yield. The second compound was identified as caryophyllene oxide by mmp, co-tlc and superimposable IR with the authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Dr. C. K. Atal, Director, RRL, Jammu for his keen interest in the work, Dr. R. K. Thappa for useful suggestions. One of the authors (M. A. Q.) is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for awarding JRF/SRF.

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